

Review Article

Role of Libraries in 21st Century

Javed Khan

Swami Vivekanand Subharti University, Meerut
E-Mail- javedsaim@gmail.com

Abstract

Libraries have existed for hundreds of years but in today's digital world, where we have at our fingertips access to an endless collection of information, a new standard of information literacy has emerged. Libraries are collections of books and other information resources gathered for the purposes of reading, study, and reference. A library as a collection or group of collections of books and/or other materials organized and maintained for use. Historically, libraries have served as places. The new role of libraries in the 21st century is to be a learning and knowledge center for their users as well as the intellectual commons for their respective communities where, to borrow the phrase from the Keystone Principles, people and ideas interact in both the real and virtual environments to expand learning and facilitate the creation of new knowledge. Libraries preserve knowledge so that none is lost, organize knowledge so that none is wasted, and make knowledge available so that no one need be deprived in this information age. Library services have brought a lot of changes to library operations there by making access to knowledge more convenient to user.

Key words: libraries, knowledge and learning, collection of information, information literacy.

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Introduction

Library/information educational programmes have a long and distinguished history. In the past, they have focused on developing physical collections of books and other materials in library buildings staffed by people who have learned to select, acquire, organise, retrieve and circulate these materials. Today library information educational programmes extend beyond the physical collections and buildings to the virtual world of the Internet. Today the concentration is on information provision to users in a variety of contexts, public, private and third sector; users who may not be necessarily able or willing to enter the library building or environment. Educational programmes are offered at the technical level, at the graduate and professional level, and at the research and doctoral level. The guidelines offered here primarily address the graduate and undergraduate levels, both of which lead to professional qualification.

Libraries are service organizations where individuals, organizations, and societies are provided unhindered access to substantial quantities of information. Libraries are collections of books and other information resources gathered for the purposes of reading, study, and reference. A library as a collection or group of collections of books and/or other materials organized and maintained for use. Historically, libraries have served as places where books used for the documentation of knowledge were kept, but they are now portals to global information relevant in education, research, individual and national development expressed either in formal or systematic language, codified in form of data, scientific formulae, etc.

The library, as a conduit for information, serving a wide spectrum of information seekers, has a critical role to play in the facilitation of knowledge generation; hence, an unhindered access to knowledge is essential in a development process.

Library: Center of Knowledge and Learning

According to Lee (2005), while the business world is changing in the new knowledge economy and digital age, libraries of all types are undergoing drastic changes also. The new role of libraries in the 21st century is to be a learning and knowledge center for their users as well as the intellectual commons for their respective communities where, to borrow the phrase from the Keystone Principles, people and ideas interact in both the real and virtual environments to expand learning and facilitate the creation of new knowledge. As a learning organization, libraries should provide a strong leadership in

knowledge management since the most important mission is to expand the access of knowledge for their users.

The importance of library to knowledge distribution can be facilitated by library services in a variety of ways, which are itemized below (Lee 2005)

- Knowledge resources management: As a result of exponential growth in human knowledge in a variety of formats, libraries must develop their resources access and sharing strategies from printed to electronic and digital resources in concert with their mission and charges;
- Resource sharing and networking: Libraries have had a long tradition of resource sharing and networking. These have been greatly expanded by the rapid development of computer, telecommunication, networking, and digital technologies and the success of which are largely as a result of the full cooperation and participation of all member libraries.
- Information technology development: To facilitate the implementation of knowledge management, a well-designed and operational knowledge management system should be in place. Latest information technology should be used as an enabler.
- User services: The utmost goal of knowledge management is to provide users with a variety of quality services in order to improve the communication, use and creation of knowledge.
- Human resource management: A great amount of expert knowledge is possessed by library staff and users, both in and outside the libraries. In university and research communities such expertise is abundant and should be inventoried, indexed, and updated regularly and be made searchable and accessible through electronic databases created and maintained by libraries. Also the transfer of knowledge and experience from experienced staff to new staff members must be encouraged.

In a nutshell, libraries preserve knowledge so that none is lost, organize knowledge so that none is wasted, and make knowledge available so that no one need be deprived in this information age.

Libraries a Bulk Storage of Knowledge in the 21st Century

Libraries have existed for hundreds of years but in today's digital world, where we have at our fingertips access to an endless collection of information, a new standard of information literacy has emerged.

The ability to connect to and search the Internet has changed the foundation of our society. Reading news stories, shopping, seeking health advice, using email to communicate, etc., have all seen revolutionary changes.

Since the beginning of the Internet, and especially since the year 2000, much was written about the changing environmental landscape and the impact it would have on libraries. The impact of the availability of full text electronic resources at a library, the library's staff and their skills, their organization or even their purpose has been well documented. This was seen primarily in the fields of science, technology and medicine.

Libraries, as critical providers of information, have an important role to play in the creation of new knowledge, arguing further that knowledge is functional at many levels. As knowledge institutions, libraries provide spaces for information-sharing and learning for all ages, genders, ethnicities, and socioeconomic groups regardless of their needs. Libraries provide the means through which new knowledge is developed and made available to all.

Technology and Library Services in the 21st Century

It is an established fact that libraries are driving access to knowledge, the question then is, why the emphasis on 21st century? Why is the 21st century different from past centuries? The truth is that, the 21st century is revolutionized by advances in computing and telecommunication technology. The 21st century has witnessed a great increase in information management and transmission. Our library learning spaces are designated Tran's disciplinary media spaces that give teachers the opportunity to conduct lessons with all of the advantages of the latest technology, and our automated library systems free up time for library professionals to focus on providing personalized assistance to students.

The new information age has brought about improved knowledge delivery, processing of information, precision, good time management and improved network system. Furthermore, information is also called data and databases are created and made accessible online via the Internet and other machine readable formats. Search engines are

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made accessible to the public. In view of this, conventional libraries seem to be giving way to hybrid and virtual libraries. (Otherwise called libraries without walls or paperless libraries) accessing or developing digital collections alongside print-based collections. We are equipping our students with the tools to gain knowledge for themselves, cultivating curiosity and inspiring life-long learning, so that they may be, now and in the future, inquisitive, judicious and informed. If education is life, libraries give us immortality.

Library services have brought a lot of changes to library operations there by making access to knowledge more convenient to user. Some of the fastest growing trends are noticed in the area of networking; file storage, graphic user interface. They have also been enabled by agreements on standards and protocols (such as Z39.50) which permit the linking together of resources from disparate sources.

- **From Multiple Locations:** From anywhere, users can consult all library holdings from workstation throughout the systematic catalog, indexing, and abstracting services. Divorcing library services from a physical location provokes a profound difference in what a library service is.
- **Availability of More Resources:** Technology now allow users to have access to diverse resources i.e. from pure bibliographical records(online catalog) now to delivery of indexing and abstracting services, course descriptions, class schedule.
- **Making Information Available in Raw Form:** Types of information available to users in digital form has continued to grow. In indexing and abstracting; search has moved from providing searchable index terms/descriptors to searchable abstracts, to more recently full-text of articles and books. In the library catalog, we have moved from bibliographic description and subject headings to providing tables of contents information, to full-text and page images. Technology has moved patrons to rawer information or more detailed representation often called enhanced records and has been a key element for those studying information retrieval.
- **Diminishing Roles for Intermediaries:** Increase interaction with online system means patron less reliance upon library staff. Patrons can check circulation information without ever contacting the circulation department.

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Challenges and Recommendations

The birth of ICT actually changed the place of libraries in terms of information acquisition and storage as well as the methods of rendering services. Despite the beautiful development, there exist basic challenges that tend to hinder the provision of access to knowledge by library. These challenges include:

- Apathy on the part of staff: Many library staff tend have an apathetic attitude towards work. They are not committed to client-oriented service.
- Lack of Maintenance Culture: Lack of maintenance culture renders infrastructures and equipment like ICT facilities non-functional.
- Poor Funding: This is the key to effective management as long as such funds are judiciously used.

The following recommendations are made to improve access to information resources in the library.

- There should be training and re-training of librarians and ICT staff in the area of computer technology and management of information services.
- The institution and library managers should be committed and work round the clock to ensure that ICT equipment and facilities are maintained regularly.
- Finally, adequate funds should be provided to ensure effective library operations.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that access to knowledge is critical for the development and growth of the society and for participation in democratic processes. The library is an integral part of the society that surrounds it. It is shaped and changed by many of the same forces that shape other types of institution. Librarians need to recognize the changes that have already taken place in libraries, and to be aware of the ways in which broader societal changes are affecting other institution. Igwe (2010) concluded that libraries provide access to an endless variety of information resources and opportunities for interactive communication. Though the fundamental mission has remained, to facilitate and give access to information and knowledge, the processes, tools and techniques have

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undergone remarkable changes. However, access alone is of course not enough, it is also about extending services, methods, and practices and developing innovative approaches to guarantee free and universal access to relevant knowledge. Libraries should ensure that the world's citizenry have access to the world's knowledge.

The library today, is a technologically driven one that uses the principles of traditional library services to organize knowledge and communicate same to clients in the global community essentially by electronic means.

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